

Innovation from Plastic

Mohamad Aidil Adan¹, Siti Amira Othman^{2*}, Che Muhammad Umair Aiman Che Jemmani³, and Muhammad Naquiuddin Razali⁴

¹ Faculty of Applied Sciences and Technology, Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, 84600, Pagoh, Johor

² Faculty of Applied Sciences and Technology, Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, 84600, Pagoh, Johor

³ Faculty of Applied Sciences and Technology, Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, 84600, Pagoh, Johor

⁴ Faculty of Applied Sciences and Technology, Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, 84600, Pagoh, Johor

* Correspondence: sitiamira@uthm.edu.my

Abstract: Plastic plays a significant role in our daily lives. It is accessible everywhere, from food to drinking water bottles to cooking utensils, whether you are at home or on the road. It is something multipurpose, portable, light, and simple to operate. Plastic adds considerable value to contemporary living and boosts the economy tremendously. Plastic packaging also contributes to food safety and waste management. Cold drinks, soft drinks, and packaged goods consumption has grown dramatically among today's generation. Plastic is perceived as extremely useful during times of need, yet it is simply discarded after use, posing a variety of risks. Although everyone enjoys these beverages, the leftover rubbish and its disposal is hazardous to both humans and the environment, resulting in plastic pollution and global warming. Because of inappropriate plastic disposal, a number of serious environmental challenges have arisen. It is one of the most rapidly growing sources of both beneficial and dangerous elements. Plastic is a non-biodegradable substance that can be hazardous for hundreds of years. Researchers discovered that plastic materials can persist for 4500 years on Earth without disintegrating. Approximately 40 million tons of municipal solid garbage are created yearly in India, with estimates growing at a rate of 1.5 to 2% each year. As a result, these waste plastics will be put to good use. This paper will review the creativity and innovation in plastic.

Keywords: plastic; packaging; non-biodegradable.

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

Plastic is derived from the Greek word *plasticos*, which meaning "able to be formed or shaped by heat". Plastic is also defined as "a material made up of a variety of synthetic or semisynthetic organic chemicals that are pliable and so can be molded into solid things." Plastic plays a significant role in our daily lives. It is accessible everywhere, from food to drinking water bottles to cooking utensils, whether you are at home or on the road. It is something multipurpose, portable, light, and simple to operate. Plastic adds considerable value to contemporary living and boosts the economy tremendously. Plastic packaging also contributes to food safety and waste management. Cold drinks, soft drinks, and packaged goods consumption has grown dramatically among today's generation. Plastic is perceived as extremely useful during times of need, yet it is simply discarded after use, posing a variety of risks. Although everyone enjoys these beverages, the leftover rubbish and its disposal is hazardous to both humans and the environment, resulting in plastic pollution and global warming. Because of inappropriate plastic disposal, a number of serious environmental challenges have arisen. It is one of the most rapidly growing sources of both beneficial and dangerous elements. Plastic is a non-biodegradable substance that can be hazardous for hundreds of years. Researchers discovered that

plastic materials can persist for 4500 years on Earth without disintegrating. Approximately 40 million tons of municipal solid garbage are created yearly in India, with estimates growing at a rate of 1.5 to 2% each year. As a result, these waste plastics will be put to good use (Gardena.com).

Plastics are accessible on the market and are classified into seven types. A number is allocated to each plastic bottle, ranging from 1 to 7. It can be written anywhere on the packaging, including the bottom, sides, and top. Some plastics are less hazardous and ecologically friendly than others, and some are much less so; some are easier to recycle than others. BPA (Bisphenol A) is a very hazardous chemical found in plastic that can cause obesity, cancer, and endocrine disorders in fetus and children. As a result, it is critical to be conscious of how plastic affects our lives. Regardless of the fact that some plastics are considered "safe," everyone should try to prevent and keep away from them as much as possible, and instead utilize glass, metal, bamboo, and other recyclable environmentally friendly materials. If people are planning to reuse plastics, keep in mind which ones are less harmful. Plastics in categories 2, 4, and 5 are thought to be reasonably safe. Number 1, 3, 6, and 7 plastics should be used with extreme caution, especially around food and drink. Plastic 1 is the worst of all and should not be recycled. When it comes to plastic packaging and food containers, everyone has consumed from a plastic bottle at some point in their lives. In such a plastic-heavy culture, it is incredibly tough to keep away from plastics, but one should attempt to prevent it as much as feasible. When people go shopping, the bulk of the things are packaged in plastic. Some of the most contaminating single-use plastics goods are readily available around us, negatively impacting our lives. To prevent using them for food, a variety of recycling methods can be implemented.

Various astonishing designs assist in the recycling of plastic bottles as well as the decoration of interior living spaces on a budget. Plastic recycling is a terrific and finest technique to reuse plastic, and it also adds to the home's attractiveness. Plastic bottles and containers may be turned into a variety of useful and ornamental products. Plastic bottles available in a range of sizes (small, medium, big, and extra-large) as well as forms; some are heavy, while others are light. All sorts are incredibly useful and helpful to recyclers and crafters for home decorating purposes since they can manufacture a variety of items, from recycled crafts to interior decorations. Every home requires a large room, whether it is referred to as a living room, drawing room or library. Plastic bottles and containers may be recycled to create new eco-friendly products for living rooms and gardens. The kitchen is the heart of the house, and women spend the majority of their time there. Various unique concepts have changed plastic bottles into a broad range of home ornaments and artworks that may be utilized to decorate kitchens in the present day. Plastic bottles are an unusual but ideal material for creating stunning frames, separators, walls, vertical gardens, flower pots, fake trees, bird/pet feeds, greenhouses, rain curtains, and aesthetic screens. Bottle caps are transformed into vibrant, spectacular, and one-of-a-kind paintings and artworks for wall decorating, outdoor strolling paths, and garden fences. It may also be used for environmentally friendly planting of money plants and other blooming plants.

2. PLASTICS

It is very tough to comprehend just how crucial plastics have been used in our daily lives. Majority of us commonly have known these materials and we take it for granted that they are usually used in nowadays daily life and all around us. Plastic have been used mainly in our daily life because it enables us to manufacturing well-designed, beautiful products using the wide variety of plastic materials accessible today. Plastics have a high level of technological expertise within manufacturing technology, as well as a variety of complex technological procedures that allow us to create and shape them in a variety of ways.

Mastering a lot of new terminology is compulsory in comprehending plastics. Some of these terms are difficult to speak. Try to speak *oxybenzylmethyleneglycolanhydride*. Instead, it might be easier to refer to this plastic by its other name, Bakelite. Strive to learn the correct vocabulary wherever

possible when discussing about plastics. Manipulating heat to shape plastics is an important aspect of practically every plastics production process.

Plastic also can be classified. Liked timbers, can be classified into hardwoods and softwoods, while metals can be divided into ferrous and nonferrous metals. But what is the classifications of plastic? These are the main types of plastics that were used in our daily life;

1. Natural plastics – These are naturally occurring materials that can be shaped and formed by manipulating heat. For example, Amber, a type of fossilized pine tree resin that is frequently used in jewelry.
2. Semi synthetic plastics – These polymers are created by combining naturally existing components with additional materials. Cellulose acetate, is an example of this material, which is a reaction of cellulose fiber and acetic acid that is used to manufacture cinema film.
3. Synthetic plastics – These are materials made by breaking down, or ‘cracking’ carbon-based materials such as crude oil, coal, or gas, and to change their molecular structure. This is usually done under heat and pressure in petrochemical refineries, and it is the first of the production processes required to make most of today's regularly occurring polymers. Plastics that are synthetic or semi-synthetic are further classified into two types. These two groups are distinguished by how various plastics react when heated.
4. Thermoplastics - Plastics that can be softened and sculpted by manipulating heat and then returned to their original shape when cooled. They will soften again if heat is applied again. Acrylic and styrene are two thermoplastics that are undoubtedly the most common in school workshops.
5. Thermosetting plastics – These are plastics that soften when heated, can be formed while still soft, and then set into the molded shape when cooled. They will not soften if heat is applied again; they will remain in the shape that they were molded into eternally. Polyester resins, which are used in glass reinforced plastics, and melamine formaldehyde, which is used to make Formica kitchen work surfaces, are examples of thermosetting plastics.

3. PLASTIC POLLUTION

Plastic pollution is the building of plastic particles and debris in the environment that has a detrimental effect on health, wildlife, and wildlife habitat. Pollutants are substances that have a negative impact on a population's health, activities, or population survival. Natural events and human actions emit thousands of tons of pollutants into the air every day. The pollutants released into the atmosphere as a result of human activity are far more hazardous. Plastics that pollute the environment are divided into three categories based on their size: micro debris plastic, mega debris plastic, and macro debris plastic.

Plastics are both inexpensive and long-lasting. These are the reasons why human plastic production is extremely high, and demand continues to rise on a routine basis. Human activities have the ability to bring human life and natural ecosystems in trouble. This is shown when plastics such as plastic bottles, plastic bags, and other packaging materials are consumed and then disposed carelessly without awareness of the consequences. When plastic debris is not properly removed or disposed of, it affects wildlife, wildlife habitat, and humans by choking and emitting a strong odor. As a result, plastic pollution has the potential to harm land, streams, and oceans (Hartline, et. al., 2016).

Most plastics have a chemical structure that makes them highly resistant towards many organic degradation processes, and as a result, it takes a long period to disintegrate. These two elements have resulted in a massive amount of plastic pollution in the environment, which is negatively impacting human health. As the human population expands dramatically, so does the need for plastic, which is being manufactured without regard for the consequences of its usage and disposal. These throwaway

products, such as water bottles, soda cans, and plastic bags, are readily disposed of, but their accumulation has resulted in an increase in plastic waste around the world.

4. CAUSE OF PLASTIC POLLUTION

The plastics causing the pollution are range in size from large to minuscule. Plastics come in a variety of forms. They exist depending on the precursors and polymerization process used. Fishing nets, regular rubbish, plastic and garbage disposal, and overuse of plastics are all major contributors to the problem of plastic pollution.

Fishing Nets - Fishing is a common agricultural activity around the world. People consume fish for their daily existence and to maintain a well-balanced diet, hence commercial fishing is an economic necessity. Plastic contamination caused by the fishing industry has caused several problems in the ocean. Plastic nets are commonly utilized for large-scale fishing activities. These fishing nets are initially immersed in water, and after a period of time, they release toxin at will. They eventually break up. This not only kills and hurts local wildlife, but it also ensures that pollutants reach the area's water and fish.

Plastic and garbage disposal - Plastics have a complex chemical composition. This makes plastic strong and resistant to degradation. Depending on their chemical composition, plastics and resins have varying capabilities for pollutant absorption and adsorption. Due to saline surroundings and the cooling action of the water, polymer breakdown takes a long time. These are elements that contribute to the persistence of plastic trash in some ecosystems. Marine specialists' findings have enabled them to forecast the rates of degradation of various plastic items. A plastic beverage holder will take 400 years, a foam plastic cup 50 years, a disposable nappy 450 years, and fishing line 600 years, according to estimates. Plastic burning is hazardous, and it can affect the environment, resulting in severe illness. As a result, if it's in a landfill, toxins will continue to leak into the environment. The majority of plastic waste in landfills comes from single-use items like packaging. When plastics are wasted or disposed in this manner, they accumulate. However, while dumping plastic garbage in landfills produces fewer greenhouse gases than incineration, landfills are limited in space. Another aspect to consider is that the liners that act as protective barriers between the landfill and the environment can break, allowing toxin to leak and contaminate the soil and water nearby (Patel & Smita).

Overuse of Plastics - This refers to the excessive use of plastics. It is less expensive and more long-lasting. These allow both the privileged and the less privileged members of society to purchase plastic materials and things. It is currently one of the most readily available and frequently used items on the planet. When plastic is disposed of or dumped, it does not quickly degrade, damaging the soil or air nearby when burned in the open air. Plastic items that are not properly dumped can also be dragged to the oceans by storms.

5. PREVENTION

The current rate of growth of plastic garbage in the globe is depressing and unjustified. People are dealing with a global plastic garbage problem that is smothering our environment and harming ecosystems. These ecosystems must be protected from further harm, and steps must be taken to create a world free of plastic trash. Industrialists have the power to alter the numerous ways in which the world uses, wastes, and recycles plastic. As a result, ecosystems, wildlife, and oceans must be recovered, and the world must be transformed into one without plastic garbage. Some of the strategies for minimizing plastic waste include:

1. Reduce - We must reduce our use of plastic in order to reduce plastic pollution. This means altering our daily habits and avoiding the use of plastic where a better alternative exists, and only using plastic when absolutely necessary. Plastic packaging should be avoided at all costs. Products such as cereals, almonds, beans, and pasta are now available in stores without packaging. Reusable bags or jars are utilized instead.
2. Recycle - To limit the amount of plastic in the waste stream, recycling entails collecting plastic waste and turning it into new items. Recycling does not reduce the amount of plastic consumed; current plastic is still used in recycling operations, but it is turned into a new one. As a result, recycling does not imply a reduction in the amount of plastic or exposure. Recycling needs to be improved because just about 14% of plastic packaging is recycled, according to research. As a result, consumers must avoid using plastic packaging and should not purchase water in plastic bottles.
3. Reuse - Re-usability refers to the ability to reuse materials in their original form rather than discarding them after each usage. This not only ensures that the material's life lifetime is maximized, but it also reduces waste. Reuse is rapidly being recognized as a critical component in tackling a variety of societal issues such as poverty, health, and well-being. It is important to make the public aware that reuse is not a waste issue. It provides goods with a second chance at life. Nonetheless, it allowed for a reduction in the usage of non-biodegradable plastic bags to some extent. Instead of tossing away bottled soft beverages, plastic goods can be reused or utilized for various uses, such as packaging processed maize, Guinea corn, millet, and other grains in Nigeria and other parts of the world. Poor plastic management can lead to pollution, albeit it does have some benefits. It is critical that humans explore how plastic can be reused. To minimize using single-use plastic bags, people can carry their own reusable shopping and produce bags to markets. Instead of using the available plastic bags, use a shopping bag. Many companies are now selling reusable water bottles as a substitute and reducing plastic waste.

6. CONCLUSION

The number of plastics consumed and really has been grown steadily. Its low density, strength, user friendly designers, fabrication capabilities, long life, low weight and low cost are the factor behind such phenomenal growth. Although plastic has many disadvantages, we can find the solution to solve the problem by make it being advantage on our daily life such as refillable. For example, whether your shampoo, conditioner, or hand cream bottle lasts a week or more, it probably happens in some kind of plastic dispenser once a month. Then it was replaced. There is a growing desire to get rid of plastic. Second, bars such as people who just want to get rid of plastic in their bathroom are increasingly turning to solid soaps and shampoos. Soap and shampoo bars are making a big comeback. Make sure they are completely wrapped in plastic and instead come in a reusable tin or box, and switching away from liquids may be the fastest solution to avoid plastic from your bathroom. Deodorant bars and creams are becoming more readily available for natural deodorants should yield a variety of results. Third, Sponges. For example, it is really simple to get a plastic-free scrub. Various doctors recommend against using washcloths or sponges in the bathroom because they can house bacteria if not properly cared for. Few people had heard of micro beads until recently, but as countries around the world became aware of this harmful addition to our creams and cosmetics, word spread, and soon governments all around the world were banning them. Micro beads, which are used for a number of functions such as exfoliation, became widely used in a short period of time as corporations moved away from more natural alternatives such as powdered apricot kernels. They are in a wide range of items, including toothpaste, sun cream, make-up, face and hand wash, and more.

After that, buy recycled plastic or plastic-free alternatives. For example, Lego, a childhood favorite, has launched a new line of plastic bricks made from sugar cane instead of wood. They have

set a deadline of 2030, when they will only utilize "bioplastic." Unfortunately, although being created from plant-based materials, bio-plastic is still plastic, and if it gets into the environment, it will behave similarly to ordinary, somewhat durable Lego bricks. In terms of preventing plastic from entering the environment, the fact that they encourage customers to pass on unwanted bricks rather than discarding them is more important. While for water gardening the advantage from that type of activity are General Potting Instructions such as Plants are typically sold as bare root stock or in pots. If they arrive potted, make sure there is enough pea gravel on top to keep the soil in, then rinse them thoroughly before adding them to your pond. For bare root stock and replanting. Water garden pots have woven-style sides and resemble baskets (like plastic laundry baskets). This facilitates the delivery of nutrients and oxygen to the plant roots. To retain the soil in the pot, line the baskets with newspaper or burlap before adding soil. The pots are flimsy, and they may lose their shape unless they're placed precisely and directly on the bottom. The smaller, square ones are a little easier to work with. Then, Adding Animal Life. For example, you might wish to add animals now that you have a living, breathing container water garden. The goldfish is the simplest and most popular.

Other options include various fish species, polliwogs, snails, and even guppies. Wait until the pond has established before adding fish or other creatures (at least a week). This will allow the water temperature and chemistry to settle, as well as plants to adjust. If the water became clogged throughout the planting process, it will settle out. After that, Maintaining Water Quality and Plant Health such as the tough part is over. One of the best things about water gardening is that it is ideal for inexperienced gardeners. There is relatively little upkeep required once your water feature is set up and has a proper balance of plants and animals. Double-check a few things while admiring feature (and feed the catch). Keep the water level steady. Do not need to add much. You may simply add less than a gallon to a 25-gallon water feature. Spritz the water in the air as much as possible. Include it This removes any chlorine from the water and adds oxygen. Last but not least, Change won't be cheap, but for too long we have been living off our planet's capital without a thought to the future. The cost of doing business as usual will far exceed the cost of correcting for our blindness.

References

- Boucher, J., & Friot, D. (n.d.). *Primary microplastics in the oceans: A global evaluation of sources*. Retrieved from <https://portals.iucn.org/library/sites/library/files/documents/2017-002.pdf>
- Cole, M., Penelope Kate Lindeque, Fileman, E. S., & Tamara Susan Galloway. (2013, May 21). *Microplastic ingestion by zooplankton*. ResearchGate; American Chemical Society. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/236926420_Microplastic_Ingestion_by_Zooplankton
- Gardena.com. *Automatic irrigation*. Retrieved from <https://www.gardena.com/int/products/guidance/automatic-irrigation/>
- Hartline, N. L., Bruce, N. J., Karba, S. N., Ruff, E. O., Sonar, S. U. and Holden, P. A. (2016). Microfiber masses recovered from conventional machine washing of new or aged garments'. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 50 (21), pp. 11532– 8.
- Joyfully Growing. (2019, June 19). How to install a drip irrigation system with automatic watering? Retrieved from <https://joyfullygrowingblog.com/automatic-drip-irrigation/>
- Patel, S., & Smita, M. (n.d.). Extent of use of empty plastic bottles in interior and exterior areas of a residence by the homemakers. Retrieved from <http://www.shabdbooks.com/gallery/268-may2020.pdf>